

Strategic Factors of Agro-Based Entrepreneurship for Rural Economic Development in Senapati District, Manipur, India

Abstract: Agro-based entrepreneurship development in rural areas has immense opportunities and empowers rural economic development. However, rural enterprise development remains very inefficient and is hindered by several challenges and difficulties relating to economic, social, political, and geographical factors. Thus, the paper is framed to explore the various entrepreneurial factors or motives associated with entrepreneurship development among agro-based entrepreneurs in the Senapati district of Manipur. The total population was 79 enterprises, out of which a sample of 50 units was selected for the study through a purposive homogeneous sampling technique. A Descriptive Statistical tool is used for comprehending the data. The study adopts a factor analysis method to elucidate the data, using the Cronbach Alpha test, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO), and the Bartlett test of sphericity through STATA software. The study revealed that the entrepreneurial factor or motive of entrepreneurs in the Senapati district is highly inclined towards the ten factors that have a high perception. This factor includes nearness to home place, own ideas, nearness to market, good transport facilities, economic necessity, nearness to raw material, to contribute to the community's welfare, to secure employment, unemployment factors, and desire to improve quality of life. Moreover, it reduces to seven broader influencing factors, i.e., Economic factors, Ambition, Infrastructure factors, social factors, social environment factors, psychological factors, and Location factors, which are important for entrepreneurship development. The study findings could help policymakers promote a better entrepreneurial environment for entrepreneurs in the Senapati district of Manipur, India.

H. Asii Doubi ¹, Dr. M. Bobo Singh ²

Affiliation

¹Research Scholar, Department of Economics, Manipur University, Imphal, Manipur.

²Professor, Department of Economics, Manipur University, Imphal, Manipur.

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Introduction

Agro-based entrepreneurship is significant for rural economic development. Because it helps harness local resources for financial gain and creates a transformative societal impact on the communities. Traditional economies still characterize the Senapati district and remain an industrial deficit region, experiencing hindrance in progress and sluggish economic growth. Thus, subsequently, promoting agro-based entrepreneurship in the district becomes a viable imperative opportunity that will empower rural populations through applying the best knowledge, promoting more people's involvement, and enhancing economic resilience against uncertainties.

Literature Review

Investment in different economic sectors is crucial for achieving prosperity, whether in the short or long term. (Meenachi I 2023), argues that investing in rural entrepreneurship serves as a mechanism for inclusive growth by creating opportunities for all societal segments, and helps promote balanced and integrated development in the rural economy. (Bredo, W 1959). Also argues that for underdeveloped countries to achieve efficient growth and broad-based economic progress, industries must be decentralized. This approach integrates industrial with rural/agricultural development and ensures that impoverished regions are brought into the mainstream economy. It is also noted that in developing the rural economy, through entrepreneurship orientation and innovative approaches is possible. (Obananya, & Gloria, 2022). According to (Singh, Lakhwinder 2006), for rural development, the role of rural industrialization is essential, by integrated involvement of farmers in agribusiness through cooperatives production, manufacturing, and marketing, alongside government-provided infrastructure and institutions; and secondly, prioritizing technological progress in the fields of agriculture and manufacturing is vital. Further, the significant role of entrepreneurship lies in

promoting the standard of living, generating employment, alleviating poverty, using local resources, and reducing rural-to-urban migration. (Ihejiamaizu and Chinonye, G, 2019). Moreover, rural entrepreneurship can be imparted by a higher density presence of training institutions, and it can significantly increase the participation of self-employed individuals in formal vocational training. This demonstrates that formal vocational training is a crucial mechanism for raising the income levels of self-employed workers in rural areas. (Bairagya, Indrajit, 2021).

On the other hand (Sandeep Saxena, 2012). Observes that rural entrepreneurs in developing regions face several distinct challenges when establishing an enterprise. These peculiar problems include illiteracy, risk aversion, a lack of training, knowledge, and experience, limited purchasing ability among the local population, and competition from urban entrepreneurs. However, (Habersetzer et al., 2020; Haladkar Mukund N., 2021). Identify some crucial factors for entrepreneurial success, particularly in rural contexts. This factor relies on the individual who has previous industry experience, operational knowledge, access to capital, motivation, business knowledge, and strong professional networks. Furthermore, entrepreneurial intention, self-confidence (self-efficacy), and support from peers, family, and institutions have a positive influence. In addition, (Martins et al., 2023). Further, emphasized that the entrepreneurial intention of the individual is significantly influenced by several key competencies: i.e., a practical knowledge of business skills, willingness to take calculated risks, and the capacity for bringing an innovation. (Ahmad et al. 2022). Emphasising identifying the pre-existing ideas of the individual, refining them, and supplementing them by conducting market research, gathering diverse information, and ultimately integrating this existing knowledge with new information is considered a highly effective process for advancing entrepreneurial development. In addition (Van Praag et al., 2007). Rural entrepreneurship is a justified development strategy because individuals with certain personal characteristics achieve better economic outcomes by becoming self-employed or business owners rather than working for a wage. (Shira Nadav et al. 2018).

Found a notable contrast in the outcomes of entrepreneurship. Although entrepreneurs typically earn lower and less stable median incomes, they report higher job and life satisfaction levels. The study attributes this greater satisfaction to entrepreneurship's ability to fulfill basic psychological needs. (Thurik, Roy et al. 2007 & Audretsch et al. 2015). Similarly, entrepreneurship venturing is also influenced by regional unemployment as a key motivator, pushing unemployed individuals to pursue start-up activities and become self-employed. Conversely, they suggested that rising in self-employment can signal an increase in entrepreneurial engagement, which may subsequently lead to a reduction in unemployment rates. Additionally, it was noted that the individual knowledge of the unemployed population's skills and expertise availability differentially affects various startups.

(Hessels et al., 2008). On the other hand, entrepreneurs were influenced by different motives like necessity motive, independence motive, and increase in wealth motive, as well as by aspirations regarding innovativeness, job growth, and export orientation. (Hanna et al. 2018). State the influence of the entrepreneurs by (1) economic factors, like (a). The desire to independently raise one's level of material (b). Capacities to gain economic independence, (c). To improve the quality of life and (2) the psychological factors related to (a). Personal self-realisation (b). The desire to increase social status; (c). To gain personal independence and autonomy; (d). To achieve professional self-fulfilment, (e). To fulfil leadership and power ambitions; (f). Corresponding with one's own ideological beliefs and values influences entrepreneurship development. (Rahman et al., 2019). In addition, several key factors shape the location selection process for SME entrepreneurs. These include the availability of open space, proximity to transport routes, like roads and rivers, and access to low-cost land. Broader economic and social dynamics also play a role, including areas with high people circulation, the advantages of business agglomeration such as mutual cooperation and clustering of related firms, and community-related issues like environmental quality, risk of eviction, and noise levels. Additionally, personal circumstances, including closeness to home,

limited capital, and existing local networks, were also identified as vital influences in deciding the business establishment location. Moreover, [Donatus et al. \(2022\)](#). The study concludes that proximity to availability of high-quality raw materials is a key factor positively influencing business location selection. Therefore, based on this review of the existing literature, it is clear that a significant study can be done regarding entrepreneurial factors that lead to entrepreneurship development in the rural district of Senapati, Manipur. Hence, this study was undertaken.

Objective of the Study

The study's main objective is to find the entrepreneurial factors that influence rural entrepreneurship development in the Senapati district of Manipur, India. Moreover, it will identify and deduce the names of the factors that are important for entrepreneurship development in the study area.

Methodology

The nature of the study is based on an exploratory approach and seeks to summarize the key characteristics and factors of rural entrepreneurs within the district. To fulfill its objective, the research focused on five subdivision blocks, i.e., Mao Maram, Purul, Paomata, and Lairouching. The sample sizes consist of 25, 8, 3, 5, and 9, respectively, resulting in a total sample of 50 units of agro-based entrepreneurs. The collection of Data used a well-structured questionnaire through purposive sampling and the personal interview technique. The questionnaire covered 18 entrepreneurial variables that influence entrepreneurs' motivation. These factors are economic necessity, unemployment, to secure self-employment, making use of idle funds, previous occupation, inspiration from others' success, family encouragement, government training, own ideas, continuation of family business, desire to improve quality of life, social recognition, fulfilling family ambitions, community welfare contributions, proximity to raw materials, market access, good transport facilities, and nearness to home. The study's sample design is presented in the accompanying Table 1. The five-point Likert scale is used, where the variable was rated from 1 to 5 on the degree of its influence: 1=To no extent, 2=To a little

extent, 3=To some extent, 4=To a great extent, 5=To a very great extent. Entrepreneurs' responses were analysed using mean scores and standard deviation, followed by ranking the factors in descending order. Factor analysis identifies the underlying patterns.

Population and Sample Design

Table 1: Sampling design

Sampling of Senapati district, Manipur, India	
A sample unit	Rural enterprise that has existed for more than 1 year
Sample element	Entrepreneurs
Sample population	79
Sample size	50, enterprise 71.42% of the population
Sampling technique	Purposive sampling

Source: Author field survey.

and achieve the study's objectives. Responses were grouped according to the resulting factor categories. To ensure the reliability and internal consistency of the data, Cronbach's Alpha test was employed. Additionally, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were conducted using STATA software to validate the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

Results and Discussion

The existing literature documented a range of factors that motivate entrepreneurs to establish enterprises. This study analysed 18 such characteristics. As shown in Table 2, the quantified responses were analysed using mean scores and standard deviation, with a weighted average of 2.43 considered as the benchmark. The Variables scoring above this average were perceived as highly influential by entrepreneurs in the district, while those below were considered less significant. The results identified ten factors with high perceived importance by the entrepreneurs and were ranked in descending order. Nearness to Home Place was ranked as the most influential factor; this attribute is due to the prevalence of home-based businesses and the convenience of the entrepreneurs. Hence, this is evidence that rural-based entrepreneurship development can be

achieved with small capital investment and create economic opportunities in rural areas. Own Ideas ranked as the second most influential factor. This highlights that self-driven initiative is a vital and fundamental trait of the entrepreneurial process. The third rank is Nearness to Market. This highlights that market access is crucial for business growth and performance. At the same time, Good Transport Facilities are ranked fourth. This underscores the vital role of connectivity and infrastructure in supporting rural enterprises. It also evidences that most enterprises are located nearby along the national highway 02, which is considered the state's lifeline. Economic Necessity is ranked fifth, indicating that entrepreneurship is often pursued to secure livelihoods and sustain income generation. This is one of the significant contributions to the rural population and economy. To contribute to the welfare of the community is ranked sixth. Hence, it strongly motivates support for community development through job creation or food security. The next is nearness to raw materials, ranked seventh,

which indicates that the value of reducing procurement costs and enhancing operational convenience is also a key factor of entrepreneurship development. To Secure Self-Employment is ranked eighth. This is due to being recognized as a pathway for creating personal employment opportunities. On the other hand, Unemployment is ranked ninth, which signifies that entrepreneurship is a response to job scarcity and a means to reduce unemployment. Lastly, Desire to Improve Quality of Life is ranked tenth. This is driven by the aspiration to achieve a higher standard of living, which is one of the common goals of every individual. The remaining factors such as government training, previous occupation, inspiration from others, family encouragement, social recognition, continuing a family business, fulfilling family ambitions, and using idle funds were ranked from 11th to 18th. They were perceived as less significant motivators in the district.

Table 2: Mean score and standard deviation from the Likert scale on key entrepreneurial factors for entrepreneurship development

Sl. No.	Entrepreneurial Factors	Motive Mean Score	σ	Rank	Decision
1	Nearness To Home Place	3.86	0.452206	1	High perception
2	Own Idea	3.74	0.59966	2	High perception
3	Nearness To Markets	3.48	0.838853	3	High perception
4	Good Transport Facilities	3.16	1.0174	4	High perception
5	Economic Necessity	3.08	0.7515975	5	High perception
6	To Contribute to The Welfare Community	3.2	0.699854	6	High perception
7	Nearness To Raw Materials	3.02	0.781417	7	High perception
8	To Secure Self-Employment	2.7	0.952976	8	High perception
9	Unemployment	2.62	0.935469	9	High perception
10	Desire To Improve Quality of Life	2.52	0.762381	10	High perception
11	Government Agencies or Training	2.02	1.097121	11	Low perception

12	Influence Of Previous Occupation	1.94	1.220209	12	Low perception
13	Inspiration From Success of Others	1.8	1.010153	13	Low perception
14	Advice or Encouragement of Family Members	1.8	0.989743	14	Low perception
15	Social Recognition	1.36	0.851409	15	Low perception
16	To Continue Family Business	1.2	0.534523	16	Low perception
17	To fulfill the Ambitions of Spouse/Parents	1.12	0.435187	17	Low perception
18	To Make Use of Idle Funds	1.1	0.364216	18	Low perception

Note: N=50, weighted average=43.8/18=2.43

σ = Standard Deviation

Source: Author field survey.

5.1. Cronbach's Alpha Test

The Cronbach Alpha Test for reliability and internal consistency of the factor variables is done. The test analysis shows the scale of the reliability coefficient as 0.7112, which signifies that the study of the 18 entrepreneurial factor variables is reliable, efficient, and justified as it falls into an acceptable range.

naming of the important factors are applied, as formulated in Table 5. This identified factor group is categorised as 1). Economic factors,

Table 3. Cronbach's alpha test

Cronbach's Alpha Test for reliability and consistency	
Average interitem covariance	.0823396
Number of items in the scale	18
Scale reliability coefficient	0.7112

Factor Principal Component Analysis

The importance of identifying the set of observed entrepreneurial variables has led to the adoption of factor analysis of entrepreneurs' responses. Moreover, the aim is to reduce the number of entrepreneurial variables. Factor analysis (principal component), which uses an orthogonal rotation matrix, has been calculated using STATA software, as shown in Table 4. Furthermore, a factor matrix was calculated from the quantified data, and then the result of a rotated component factor matrix was determined to group factor variables above 0.5. The factor variable that falls below the tolerance level of 0.5 is dropped from the factor grouping. Based on the loaded value, identification and

Table 4: Rotated component matrix extracted with Principal Component Matrix and Sorted Factor Loading

	Component						
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6	Factor 7
TSSE	0.8872	-0.0879	-0.0866	-0.0256	-0.1357	-0.0347	0.1945
UN	0.8867	-0.0246	-0.0497	-0.1074	-0.1079	-0.1550	-0.0667
EN	0.6334	0.4338	0.2195	0.0411	-0.0406	0.0316	-0.0846
ISO	0.1141	-0.7287	-0.1459	0.3264	0.2158	0.0599	0.1140
DTIQL	0.0108	0.7218	0.1562	0.0958	0.3686	0.2572	-0.1917
OI	0.1194	0.6498	0.0690	0.1720	-0.0183	0.0693	0.3971
GAT	0.0911	-0.5001	-0.1486	-0.4398	0.3549	-0.1105	0.1156
GTF	-0.0412	0.0917	0.8876	0.1130	-0.0803	0.1639	0.1851
NTM	-0.0467	0.1172	0.8826	0.0736	0.0631	0.0395	0.0201
TMUIF	-0.1037	-0.1527	0.7282	0.0072	0.0343	0.0275	0.0092
SR	-0.1681	0.2119	0.2002	0.6093	0.1408	0.4702	0.0472
IPO	0.1254	0.2159	0.4489	0.5247	-0.2720	0.1774	-0.0506
TCTWC	0.0647	0.2208	0.0426	0.7161	0.7535	0.0098	0.0515
NTRM	-0.2941	-0.1550	0.0562	0.0619	0.7085	0.1875	0.3181
TCFB	-0.3111	0.1761	-0.2173	-0.0308	-0.5725	-0.0054	0.3014
TFASP	-0.0756	0.0038	0.1524	0.3098	0.3239	0.8561	0.1273
AOEFM	-0.3264	0.0808	0.0653	0.2984	0.1946	0.5758	0.3436
NTHP	0.1017	-0.0642	0.2219	-0.1469	-0.0837	-0.0534	0.8125

Sources: Author analysis of rotated factor principal component.

Note: Factors with variable loads above 0.5 are highlighted, and the abbreviation in Table 4. stands for the following. To secure self-employment (TSSE), unemployment (UN), Economic Necessity (EN), Inspiration from other success (ISO), Desire to improve quality of life (DTIQL), Own Ideas (OI), Government agencies or training (GAT), Good transport facilities, (GTF), Nearness to market (NTM), To make used of idle

fund (TMUIF). Social recognition (SR), Influence of previous occupation (IPO), To contribute to welfare community (TCTWC), Nearness to raw material (NTRM), To continue family Business (TCFB), To fulfill the ambition of spouse or parent (TFASP), Advice or encouragement of family members (AOEFM), and Nearness to home place (NTHP).

Table 5. Identifying and clubbing important entrepreneurial factors motive

Variable factors, motive	Factors. no	Factors Name
1. To Secure Self-Employment, Unemployment, Economic Necessity	1	Economic factors
2. Desire to Improve Quality of Life, Own Ideas	2	Ambition
3. Good Transport Facilities, Nearness to Market	3	Infrastructure factors
4. To Make Use of Idle Funds, Social Recognition, Influence of Previous Occupation	4	Social Factors
5. To Contribute to the Welfare Community, Nearness to Raw Materials	5	Social environment factors
6. To Fulfill Ambitions of Spouse/Parents, Advice or Encouragement of Family Members	6	Psychological factors
7. Nearness to home place	7	Location factors

KMO measures and Barlett's test

Table 6. KMO measures of sample adequacy and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	Measure of sample adequacy	0.504
Bartlett test of sphericity	Chi-square	332.690
	Degrees of freedom	153
	p-value	0.000

Source: Author computation based on primary data.

In addition, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test is done to check the sample data's suitability for factor analysis. The test result of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin shows 0.504, which is above the threshold level of 0.5. This result indicates that factor analysis was significant. Similarly, Bartlett's test of sphericity was also done to confirm the suitability of factor analysis. The Bartlett test of sphericity is significant at the p-value 0.000, which is much less than 0.05. This indicates that the variables are correlated, and the dataset results from factor analysis signify that the study is very useful.

Conclusion

All Entrepreneurs show a high influence of the nearness to home and rank first. This is due to the fact that agro-based entrepreneurship is operated on a small scale within the convenience of the household. The role of location conveniences and suitability plays a vital part in entrepreneurial undertakings. It also found that entrepreneurs' own ideas ranked second. This indicates that the individual was self-motivated and reflects that they have a strong sense of determination to become an entrepreneur. It was also observed that proximity to the market ranked third. This reflects that market accessibility is very significant as it makes them more convenient in terms of sales and the supply chain of goods and services. All the entrepreneurs preferred good transport facilities and ranked fourth. This implies the importance of infrastructure-like connectivity. In the fifth, it was ranked on economic necessity, highlighting that entrepreneurship ensures their livelihood sustenance. The hope of bringing

social change and community upliftment also influences the entrepreneurial journey, thereby contributing to a Welfare Community, which is ranked sixth. It was followed by Nearness to Raw Materials, which denotes that easy access to raw materials is an important determinant for entrepreneurship development, and ranked seventh. It was also found that to have job opportunities, entrepreneurs need to venture into entrepreneurship. Thus, securing self-employment is ranked eighth. And unemployment ranks ninth. Hence, entrepreneurship ensures the promotion of effective employment and work culture. Lastly, Desire to Improve Quality of Life is ranked tenth. Thus, entrepreneurship gives the hope of achieving a better living standard and influences entrepreneurship development. The other variable factors, such as Government Agencies or Training, Influence of Previous Occupation, Inspiration from Success of Others, Advice or Encouragement of Family Members, Social Recognition, To Continue Family Business, To Fulfil the Ambitions of Spouse/Parents, and To Make Use of Idle Funds rank from 11 to 18 respectively which fall into less significant influence among the entrepreneurs. Therefore, after analysing all influential factors, it is suggested that the following are the key important factors for entrepreneurship development in the Senapati district. i.e., 1). Economic factors, 2). Ambition, 3). Infrastructure factor, 4). Social factors, 5). Social environment factors, 6). Psychological factors and lastly, 7). Location factors. Without the above seven factors, the effectiveness of developing agro-based entrepreneurship in the district will remain immobile.

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